

STRUCTURE OF FORMATION OF STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES IN HIGHER TECHNICAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the preparation of competitive, competent transport engineers for market relations and the important tasks identified therein. The structure of the formation of professional competencies of transport engineers and the need for widespread use of ICT capabilities in its formation are also mentioned.*

Keywords: *professional competence, engineer, work activity, knowledge, education, profession, skill.*

Introduction. Nowadays, in the conditions of modern development, production technologies and economic globalization, new requirements are being imposed on the educational process in the preparation of future transport engineers[1]. Today, a professional approach to education alone is not enough. Higher education, along with preparing a new generation of specialists for work, should also prepare a knowledgeable, critical-thinking person who has accepted certain cultural standards, national values, and ethical principles [2]. This young specialist should understand the moral value of actions and choices in the work process, national cultural values, and have the ability to communicate interculturally. Today, employers want future transport engineers to have, in addition to professional knowledge and skills, new abilities such as teamwork, creativity, foresight, resourcefulness, learning and adapting to changes, efficiency, and accountability.

Modernization of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan involves training personnel based on the development of the current economy, science, culture, technology and technology. Highly qualified, competent human capital has become the main resource in today's modernization. One of the main goals of education is the development of professional competencies of future engineers. A comprehensive approach is an objective requirement of modern education.

Analysis of the literature on the topic. The implementation of the approach to the formation of competencies of transport engineers in higher educational institutions will lead to the acceleration of the processes of globalization and the development of information technologies in the world [3,4].

In the current socio-economic conditions, there is a high demand not for the model of functional training of graduates of higher educational institutions, strictly focused on specific objects and subjects of labor, but for the model of training graduates with developed professional competencies. In the new structure of higher education, the purpose, content and results of graduate training are formed in a complex and integrated manner, taking into account changes in professional activity, and are not limited to the functional area of their application. Such a structure includes the professional qualifications and basic personal qualities of the graduate, determined by

the system of knowledge, skills and qualifications, as well as systematically formed universal skills and qualifications, which are defined as basic competencies in current international practice [5]. The formation of professional competencies is currently perceived as the process of assimilating social experience and, on this basis, the formation of individual experience of students in solving informational personal problems.

Based on the requirements of today, knowledge of information and communication technologies and foreign languages is a must to become a qualified transport engineer. Currently, it is necessary to further expand the role of information and communication technologies to increase the professional competencies of students[6]. Integration of basic and professional training determines the understanding of readiness for successful professional activity. To solve the problem of forming professional competence of students of technical universities in the process of teaching specialties and specialties, a professional structure of training has been developed and conditions for its activity have been created.

Research methodology. According to the proposed structure, a student will be ready for future activity only if he can participate in design processes and work with modern technologies in solving problems in the field of his future professional activity by applying fundamental knowledge. To achieve such a result, it is necessary to eliminate the major shortcomings associated with traditional training. We can attribute these shortcomings to the ineffective management of students' cognitive activity [7].

This activity is associated with the teacher's approach to a specific student, and the teacher directly receives information about the quality of students' learning of the material during lessons and independent work, and their knowledge is supported throughout the process. If you use interactive teaching methods that include a set of pedagogically effective tools, the correction of shortcomings will be more effective. We believe that it is necessary to establish several educational criteria for the effective functioning of the structure of the formation of students' professional competencies.

First, the level of knowledge of information and communication technologies. In this case, in the process of studying specialized subjects with the help of information and communication technologies, the readiness of students of technical universities for professional activity is formed and its multi-stage monitoring is made possible. It forms sufficient information search skills of students to improve their professional knowledge in their specialty[8].

Secondly, the level of knowledge of foreign languages. Sufficient knowledge of foreign languages by future transport engineers opens up wide opportunities for improving their professional knowledge.

Thirdly, the level of application of theoretical knowledge in practice. In order to strengthen the integration of science, education and production, the topics of students' coursework, course projects, practical and laboratory exercises, and qualification practices are formed based on the existing problems in the system, and students are formed with the skills to independently solve these problems.

Fourthly, the level of participation in design processes. Increasing the participation of students in innovative projects (practical, fundamental). Wide use of ICT capabilities in the formulation of project tasks[9]. Also, in creating a design environment, in addition to the project manager, advice from ICT teachers, leading experts in the chosen field, and professional professors of specialized disciplines is very important. Monitoring the level of student participation in design processes is carried out during lectures and practical exercises in the field of IT technologies or

with its help. Such processes are based on the use of experimentally equipped classrooms with the possibility of feedback, organized in the environment of an automated management system for students' cognitive activities. Such an auditorium will be equipped with personal computers for students. The teacher can conduct a survey in the form of a test and then receive information about the level of assimilation of information, the level of readiness of students to implement and master new material in real time.

Urgench State University uses project-based approaches to train students in the field of "Transport Engineering". The project-oriented approach to train students of technical universities implies an approach based on independent project work of students, aimed at solving problem situations identified on the basis of the interrelationship between general and specialized disciplines [10].

Starting from the first year of education, students participate in solving problems related to their professional orientation in the process of studying information and communication technologies. Students solve problems that may arise in their professional activities in the future. Such tasks are coordinated with the areas in which students receive knowledge. When analyzing tasks, students create ideas that they can implement in their micro and macro projects.

To implement a competency-based approach to the project, the following steps should be taken:

- At the first preparatory stage, the specifics of project activities and their significance for engineers should be explained.
- At the second stage, students learn to work individually during project activities. The teacher should create an opportunity for each student to be able to self-manage ICT in the process of learning, to feel their main task in order to better understand their future professional activities, and to learn how to use ICT knowledge in their future professional activities.
- At the third stage, students should learn how to conduct group projects. The teacher should teach students to work in a team, taking a creative approach to solving professional tasks.

The transition of students to project-oriented independent activity should be carried out in an environment of "student - ICT teachers, leading experts in the chosen field and professors of specialized disciplines", since the organization of student activities by professional teachers of the subject area and ICT teachers helps to identify the most pressing issues that are part of the professional activity of the future transport engineer in specialized disciplines.

Using the design method to form students' professional competencies, we aimed to help all students activate their educational activities not only in preparing them to master new knowledge, but also in perceiving and understanding new theoretical material: to form in them the skills of observation, finding important features, developing new concepts, rules, conclusions and proposals.

Analysis and results. We have developed a structural and theoretical functional structure of the formation of students' professional competencies in the study of the indicated general and specialized disciplines. The structure includes four block components, each of which performs a specific task, and we have developed criteria for the formation of professional competencies. Let's consider each component and the functions it performs (Figure 1).

The implementation of the structure includes the preparatory, formation and final stages of the implementation of the organizational and operational structure of the formation of

competencies among future transport engineers. One of the problems that future transport engineers solve is the provision of timely transport services to consumers. To fulfill this task, it is necessary to form the skills of providing customer service using ICT (mobile applications) in students. To do this, it is necessary to convey to students the essence of the content of ICT programs used in the transport sector in our country and in developed foreign countries, and to form the skills of solving existing problems and making the right decisions in various situations using them. This will help to win in a competitive environment and take their Place.

Figure 1. Theoretical functional structure of the formation of professional competencies.

Awareness of these methods allows students to form professional competencies necessary for their professional activities. The selection of project tasks for professional activities is carried out by combining professional and fundamental knowledge. The selection of tasks is carried out

in accordance with the following requirements: compliance with state educational standards, compliance with the level of student training and relevance to future professional activities.

As indicated above, an important stage in the study of ICT is setting tasks for students that are relevant to their future work. In the initial part, students discuss the tasks in the classroom and check them to identify problem situations. They often arise from the lack of correlation between the problematic tasks of the professional activities of future transport engineers and ICT. The formation of the idea of solving ICT tasks can be carried out within the framework of a general project. Initially, students implement their own professional projects, and then transform them into a complete and integrated project. The development, presentation, and evaluation of the project will be carried out with the direct participation of the ICT teacher and specialized subject teachers. The implementation of the proposed procedure can be considered on the example of the problem of transport services.

It should be noted that the lesson time is often not enough to study the main topics of the subject "Fundamentals of the organization of transportation and traffic safety in automobiles". Therefore, students are required to independently study the selection of a supplier, selection problems, the main factors taken into account in the selection, the optimal size of the supply, the delivery interval, and the description of the quality indicators of the supply. After that, students will have professional competence in selecting a supplier.

Individual projects developed by students in the field of transport are included in a single, integrated macro-project. Project work is completed after a presentation on student reports at various levels. The student team implementing the macro-project can invite students defending their project to answer test tasks on their reports, thereby encouraging them to actively participate in the discussion.

Conclusion. The level of formation of students' professional competencies is assessed based on the goals of professional activity, the goals that future transport engineers want to achieve within the framework of the project, and the methods they choose to achieve the goal:

I reproductive level (low) is characterized by several positive motives for future professional activity. Basically, this is due to the low level of professional skills of the transport engineer in the process of his activity, avoidance of the inability to fulfill the tasks specified in his job description, or having very few personal motives.

II variant level (medium) - this is a future transport engineer with a high interest in professional activity, but not having sufficient professional competencies in his profession. In this case, the motives are related only to the production side, and in order to achieve successful results, he must have deeper theoretical knowledge.

Level III creativity (high) - a future transport engineer can independently and creatively perform the assigned tasks without the help of a teacher. He has formed professional competencies in foreign languages, using ICT, participating in scientific projects and implementing professional knowledge in production. Thus, the proposed structure was tested with students of the "Transport Engineering" educational program at UrSU and confirmed the increased interest of future transport engineers in acquiring new knowledge and the formation of professional competencies.

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